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Application of (4, 2)-jection Operator in Exponential and Hyperbolic Functions

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Abstract:

In this paper, we use (4, 2)-jection operator which is the generalization of projection operator, projection defined in G.F. Simmons [1]. We have define e^B , where B is a (4, 2)-jection operator on a linear space L .

We find e^{nB} , n being an integer. We define hyperbolic function related to a (4, 2)-jection operator B . We deduce properties of hyperbolic function such as $\cosh^2 B - \sinh^2 B = I$, etc. We prove results analogous to results in trigonometry.

Keywords: linear space, projection operator, Hyperbolic functions, Trijection operator, (4, 2)-jection.

1. Introduction:

(4, 2)-jection and hyperbolic functions:-

Definitions:

Let B be a (4, 2)-jection operator on a linear space L . [2]
i.e. $B^4 = B^2$.

We define,

$$e^B = I + B + \frac{B^2}{2!} + \frac{B^3}{3!} + \frac{B^4}{4!} + \frac{B^5}{5!} + \frac{B^6}{6!} + \dots$$

Now, $e^B = I + B + \frac{B^2}{2!} + \frac{B^3}{3!} + \frac{B^2}{4!} + \frac{B^3}{5!} + \frac{B^2}{6!} + \dots$ (if $B^4 = B^2$)

$$= I + B + B^2 \left(\frac{1}{2!} + \frac{1}{4!} + \frac{1}{6!} + \dots \right) + B^3 \left(\frac{1}{3!} + \frac{1}{5!} + \frac{1}{7!} + \dots \right)$$

$$= I + B + B^2 \left(\frac{e^1 + e^{-1}}{2} - 1 \right) + B^3 \left(\frac{e^1 - e^{-1}}{2} - 1 \right)$$

$$e^B = I + B + B^2(\cosh 1 - 1) + B^3(\sinh 1 - 1)$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
(e^B)^2 &= [I + B + B^2(\cosh 1 - 1) + B^3(\sinh 1 - 1)]^2 \\
&= [I^2 + B^2 + B^4(\cosh 1 - 1)^2 + B^6(\sinh 1 - 1)^2 + 2.I.B \\
&\quad + 2.B.B^2(\cosh 1 - 1) + 2.B^2(\cosh 1 - 1)B^3(\sinh 1 - 1) \\
&\quad + 2.I.B^3(\sinh 1 - 1) + 2.I.B^2(\cosh 1 - 1) + 2.B.B^3(\sinh 1 - 1)] \\
&= [I^2 + B^2 + B^2(\cosh 1 - 1)^2 + B^2(\sinh 1 - 1)^2 + 2.B \\
&\quad + 2.B^3(\cosh 1 - 1) + 2.B^3(\cosh 1 - 1)(\sinh 1 - 1) \\
&\quad + 2.B^3(\sinh 1 - 1) + 2.I.B^2(\cosh 1 - 1) + 2.B.B^3(\sinh 1 - 1)] \\
&= [I^2 + B^2 + B^2(\cos^2 h1 + \sin^2 h1 - 1) + B^3(2\sinh 1 \cosh 1 - 2)] \\
&= [I^2 + B^2 + B^2(\cos 2h1 - 1) + B^3(\sin 2h1 - 2)] \\
(e^B)^2 &= [I^2 + 2B^2 + B^2(\cos 2h1 - 1) + B^3(\sin 2h1 - 2)]
\end{aligned}$$

Let us assume,

$$(e^B)^n = [I^2 + nB^2 + B^2(\cosh n1 - 1) + B^3(\sinh n1 - n)]$$

Now, $(e^B)^{n+1} = (e^B)^n \times e^B$

$$\begin{aligned}
&[I + B + B^2(\cosh 1 - 1) + B^3(\sinh 1 - 1)] \times [I^2 + nB^2 + B^2(\cosh n1 - 1) + B^3(\sinh n1 - n)] \\
&= [I + nB + B^2(\cosh n1 - 1) + B^3(\sinh n1 - n) + B + nB^2 + B^3(\cosh n1 - 1) \\
&\quad + B^4(\sinh n1 - n) + B^2(\cosh 1 - 1) + nB^3(\cosh 1 - 1) + B^4(\cosh 1 - 1)(\cosh n1 - 1) \\
&\quad + B^5(\cosh 1 - 1)(\sinh n1 - n) + B^3(\sinh n1 - 1) + nB^4(\sinh 1 - 1) \\
&\quad + B^5(\cosh n1 - 1)(\sinh 1 - n) + B^6(\sinh 1 - 1)(\sinh n1 - n)] \\
&= I + (nB + B) + B^2 \{ \cosh n1 - 1 + n + \sinh n1 - n + \cosh 1 - 1 \\
&\quad + (\cosh 1 - 1)(\cosh n1 - 1) + n(\sinh 1 - 1) + (\sinh 1 - 1)(\sinh n1 - n) \} \\
&\quad + B^3 \{ \sinh n1 - n + \cosh 1 - 1 + n(\cosh 1 - 1) + (\cosh 1 - 1)(\sinh n1 - n) \\
&\quad + (\sinh 1 - 1) + (\sinh 1 - 1)(\cosh n1 - 1) \}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= I + (n + 1)B + B^2 \{ \cosh 1 \cdot \cosh n 1 + \sinh 1 \cdot \sinh n 1 - 1 \} + B^3 \{ \cosh 1 \cdot \sinh n 1 \\
 &+ \sinh 1 \cdot \cosh n 1 - n - 1 \} \\
 &= I + (n + 1)B + B^2 \{ \cosh(n + 1) - 1 \} + B^3 \{ \sinh(n + 1) - (n + 1) \}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence by induction for any positive integer n .

$$e^{nB} = [I^2 + nB^2 + B^2(\cosh n 1 - 1) + B^3(\sinh n 1 - n)]$$

if we put $n = 0$,

$$e^{0B} = [I^2 + 0.B^2 + B^2(\cos 0h1 - 1) + B^3(\sin 0h1 - 0)]$$

$$e^0 = [I^2 + 0 + B^2(1 - 1) + B^3(0 - 0)]$$

$$e^0 = I, \text{ where } 0 \text{ is zero operator.}$$

So relation holds when $n = 0$.

So we take

$n = -n$, i.e. when n is a negative integer.

$$e^{-nB} = [I + (-n)B^2 + B^2(\cos(-n)h1 - 1) + B^3(\sin(-n)h1 - (-n))]$$

$$e^{-nB} = [I - nB^2 + B^2(\cosh n 1 - 1) - B^3(\sinh n 1 - n)]$$

Putting $B = I$

$$e^{nI} = [I^2 + nI^2 + I^2(\cosh n 1 - 1) + I^3(\sinh n 1 - n)]$$

$$= I[I + n + \cosh n 1 - 1 + \sinh n 1 - n]$$

$$e^{nI} = I[\cosh n 1 + \sinh n 1]$$

So we put $n = 1$

$$e^I = I[\cosh 1 + \sinh 1]$$

$$e^I = Ie \text{ or } eI$$

Now,

$$\cosh B = I + \frac{B^2}{2!} + \frac{B^4}{4!} + \frac{B^6}{6!} + \dots; \text{ (if } B^4 = B^2 \text{)}$$

$$= I + \frac{B^2}{2!} + \frac{B^2}{4!} + \frac{B^2}{6!} + \dots$$

$$= I + B^2 \left[\frac{1}{2!} + \frac{1}{4!} + \frac{1}{6!} + \dots \right]$$

$$= I + B^2 \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{2!} + \frac{1}{4!} + \frac{1}{6!} + \dots \right) - 1 \right]$$

$$\cosh B = I + B^2 [\cosh 1 - 1]$$

$$\sinh B = B + \frac{B^3}{3!} + \frac{B^5}{5!} + \frac{B^7}{7!} + \dots; \text{ (if } B^4 = B^2 \text{)}$$

$$\sinh B = B + \frac{B^3}{3!} + \frac{B^3}{5!} + \frac{B^3}{7!} + \dots$$

$$= B + B^3 \left[\frac{1}{3!} + \frac{1}{5!} + \frac{1}{7!} + \dots \right]$$

$$= B + B^3 \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{3!} + \frac{1}{5!} + \frac{1}{7!} + \dots \right) - 1 \right]$$

$$\sinh B = B + B^3 [\sinh 1 - 1]$$

Now,

$$\sinh B + \cosh B = B + B^3 [\sinh 1 - 1] + I + B^2 [\cosh 1 - 1]$$

$$e^B = I + B + B^2 [\cosh 1 - 1] + B^3 [\sinh 1 - 1]$$

$$e^{2B} = I + 2B + B^2 [\cosh 2 - 1] + B^3 [\sinh 2 - 2]$$

$$e^{nB} = I + nB + B^2 [\cosh n - 1] + B^3 [\sinh n - n]$$

$$e^{nB} = \{I + B^2(\cosh n - 1)\} + \{nB + B^3(\sinh n - n)\}$$

$$e^{nB} = \sinh nB + \cosh nB$$

Theorem (1.I): $\cosh^2 nB - \sinh^2 nB = I$

Proof: $\cosh nB + \sinh nB$

$$= \{I + B^2(\cosh n - 1)\} + \{nB + B^3(\sinh n - n)\}$$

$$= e^{nB}$$

Now,

$$\cosh nB - \sinh nB$$

$$= \{I + B^2(\cosh n - 1)\} - \{nB + B^3(\sinh n - n)\}$$

$$= e^{-nB}$$

$$\cosh^2 nB - \sinh^2 nB$$

$$= (\cosh nB + \sinh nB)(\cosh nB - \sinh nB)$$

$$= e^{nB} \times e^{-nB}$$

$$= e^0$$

$$= I$$

Hence, $\cosh^2 nB - \sinh^2 nB = I$

Theorem (1.II): $\cosh nB \cdot \operatorname{sech} nB = I$

Proof: We know that

$$\operatorname{sech} nB = I + B^2(\operatorname{sech} n - 1)$$

$$\therefore \cosh nB \cdot \operatorname{sech} nB$$

$$= \{I + B^2(\cosh n - 1)\} \cdot \{I + B^2(\operatorname{sech} n - 1)\}$$

$$= [I + B^2(\operatorname{sech} n - 1) + B^2(\cosh n - 1) + B^4(\cosh n - 1)(\operatorname{sech} n - 1)] \text{ (if } B^4 = B^2)$$

$$= I + B^2[\operatorname{sech} n - 1 + \cosh n - 1 + 1 + \cosh n - \operatorname{sech} n + 1]$$

$$= I + B^2[0]$$

$$= I$$

Theorem (1.III): $(\cosh B + \sinh B)^n = (\cosh nB + \sinh nB)$

Proof: R.H.S

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\cosh nB + \sinh nB) &= \{I + B^2(\cosh n - 1)\} + \{nB + B^3(\sinh n - n)\} \\
 &= [I + nB + B^2(\cosh n - 1) + B^3(\sinh n - n)] \\
 &= e^{nB} = (e^B)^n \\
 &= [I + B + B^2(\cosh 1 - 1) + B^3(\sinh 1 - 1)]^n \\
 &= [\{I + B^2(\cosh 1 - 1)\} + \{B + B^3(\sinh 1 - 1)\}]^n \\
 &= (\cosh B + \sinh B)^n
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem (1.IV): $(I + \cosh 2 + \sinh 2)^n = 2^n \cosh^n B (\cosh nB + \sinh nB)$

Proof: $(I + \cosh 2 + \sinh 2)^n = \{I + \cosh^2 B + \sinh^2 B + 2\sinh B \cosh B\}^n$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (\cos^2 hB + \sin^2 hB + 2\sinh B \cosh B)^n \\
 &= \{2\cosh B(\cosh B + \sinh B)\}^n \\
 &= 2^n \cosh^n B (\cosh B + \sinh B)^n \\
 &= 2^n \cosh^n B (\cosh nB + \sinh nB)
 \end{aligned}$$

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